

NATURE- CASTE RELATION: A READING OF URMILA PAWAR'S "AAYDAN" (THE WEAVE OF MY LIFE)

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ABSTRACT

Human survival is directly tied to our relationship with the natural environment. However, the historic continuum can be seen where the control over resources is wielded by the privileged, relegating the marginalized communities to a perpetual state of subjugation and dispossession. In this context, Dalits in the Indian social context bear the weight of environmental injustices. Urmila Pawar through her autobiography "Aaydan" dissects the layers of environmental injustice levied upon the Dalit people, the inaccessibility of drinking water, the way they were not allowed to use the roads used by the upper caste, rather rough deadly terrain was left for them for daily work. Moreover, the food disparity faced by them projects the patterns of power, privilege and marginalization that shape the relationship with the nature. Having all these, the paper also focused on the spiritual connection of the dalits with the nature. Nature for them remains their place of existence, the state of survival; Pawar present how they are so connected with the natural sphere focusing on their psychological understanding of nature and its various elements.

Keywords: Caste, Dalit, Environmental Casteism, Nature, Hierarchy, Injustice

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Eco-criticism as an object of study has proven to be more dynamic as it is proven to provide light on ecological concerns but also encourages readers to think their relationship with the natural world. Advocating the deep attachments with nature has laid the foundation for the eco-literary movement. Eco-literary works sought to blend personal reflection, natural observation and philosophical contemplation, "Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism" by William Rueckert in the late 1970s introduced the term "ecocriticism" where he called for a critical approach that would explore the ecological dimensions of literature and consider how literary texts interact with the environment.

Urmila Pawar's "Aaydan" being a Dalit narrative talks about the subjugation faced by the Dalit community by the upper class society resulting in inappropriate distribution of basic needs for the survival of human. Historic continuum can be seen where control over resources is wielded by the privileged, relegating the marginalized communities to a perpetual state of subjugation and dispossession. The upper class design of proportions signifies the hegemonic principles and exploitation of the dalit people. As an autobiography Pawar tries to depict the cultural domain and the practices of the dalit community and how nature is used to objectify the life of these dalit people. Dalits bear the weight of environmental injustice which dissect the layers of environmental injustice revealing the intricate patterns of power, privilege and marginalization that shapes our relationship with the environment throwing light on eco-consciousness. In understanding the environmental justice, social justice remains frequent in terms of environmental inequalities such as "exclusion, discrimination, harms, victimization, distribution, access and rights and their relevance to specific social group". Urmila Pawar shows how nature plays the role for the survival of the dalit community as most of their earning comes from weaving baskets from natural sources, as the title of the autobiography itself works as an indicating factor. At the very starting of the book we see Pawar's mother weaving baskets as a customary practices of their community. After the death of her husband Pawar's Aai(mother) has been weaving baskets for the survival of their family. Nature always acted as a guiding factor for these dalit people especially with the dalit women who got everything from nature to run their families, "Women from our village travelled to the market at Ratnagiri to sell various things. They trudged the whole distance, with huge, heavy bundles on their heads, filled with firewood or grass rice or semolina, long pieces of bamboo, baskets of ripe or raw mangoes".

The Dalit community co-exists with nature as nature acts as their chief benefactor, from collection of firewood to the basic necessities of survival, Dalit people's lifestyles revolves around nature. Their primitive existence with nature influences lives and how nature plays the significant roles in terms of survival. Their foremost decisions regarding choice of work has the influence of nature in abundance; they consist mostly of doing jobs based on labour, like collecting firewood, fruits, vegetables, fish, baskets. Moreover, the way caste hierarchies perpetuate through the exploitation of nature, caste and nature are in fact interconnected and interwoven in the Indian society. The ecological determination of caste provides the justification of caste system through nature. Dalit's identity becomes visible the way they are placed in nature by the brahmanical society, it creates the power relation and social order thus creating the binary idea of purity and impurity.

Human survival is directly tied to our relationship with the natural environment; the ecocentric worldview is “nature-centered” and assumes that humans are a part of the natural world. “Dalits have had a long history of social and environmental struggles which have manifested in regular conflicts against Brahmin and Savarna (higher caste) domination of eco-space, as well as in assertion and creation of an autonomous Dalit eco-space”. But in the broad approach of ecocriticism, the focus on environmental casteism gave access to various dimensions of caste discrimination meted out to the Dalits thus leading to the socio-ecological movements espoused by Dr.B.R.Ambedkar representing the unheard and unacknowledged voices at the margin of the Hindu social structure. During the Mahar movement on 20 March 1927 Ambedkar tried to shape the paradigm of environmental justice in India by citing the inaccessibility of water around a village in Maharashtra. It was the first public assertion of the rights of Dalit as citizens to access natural resources such as water, as for dalits water is not only an object for daily use but constant sets of struggle and conflict. Movements like the Mahar movements holds some of the fundamental themes of environmental and social justice like Dalits access, ownership, rights and participation in land, water, forests and commons. Economic deprivation forms a concern for many dalit narratives which shows hunger and struggle for food from very near. Urmila Pawar defines the ‘dalits’ as a “human being crushed under the heels of the social order dominated by the oppressive caste system, a neglected, ignored entity yet who had stood up to resist it with a rationalist humanist ideology”. Pawar has tried to focus on the natural life of these dalit people especially the dalit women through her autobiography “Aaydan” (The Weave of My Life) that also shows how these dalit peoples’ life are associated with the ecology. The interconnectedness and collaboration between the Dalit community and natural environment that surrounds them has the greatest significance in terms of survival. She has glorified the relation of the dalit lives with nature, no matter how hard the women find to cross the stiff rocky deadly hills, the fierceful Mirjole River, their life’s grit with the nature, it teaches them the hardship and calmness in life. The romanticization of nature in her work remains the embodiment of the environmental perspectives, the harmony which persists amongst the dalit women is due to their understanding of each other and their work which is surrounded around nature. It is worthy to mention that Pawar through her narrative narrates that the life of the dalits and their livelihood is all about the nature. They are having more environmental conscious and we get to know it in the preface of the “Aaydan”. Before plastic began to be utilized for making different objects of everyday use, bamboo was the most common material used to make baskets, containers, and other things of general utility in households. Aaydan is the generic term used for all things made from bamboo; awata is another word outside the Konkan, the job of weaving bamboo baskets has traditionally been assigned to nomadic tribes like the Barud. In the Konkan region, however it was the Mahar caste which undertook this task. Nobody knows why even today, the practice, though considerably weaker, is still prevalent. The other meanings of aaydan are ‘utensil’ and ‘weapon’. When we analyses the words, we get a clear perspectives that how dalit community and their cultural practices have always been an integral part of nature. Nature acts as a protective weapon for them and their entire livelihood depends on nature. Even after marriage she saw how her mother-in-law took keen interest in relying on nature and she used to be very proud of herself for being able to relate herself with nature so profoundly and thereby-taking pride in doing agricultural work,

taking care of their cattle etc; such close association with nature makes their life full and makes them feel free from prejudices and hierarchical framework.

Nature is seen as the predominant factor in Pawar's "Aaydan", it seeks to see how dalit culinary traditions developed across the country as a mode of survival, born from economic necessity and the need to adopt. Food practices were never made out of choice but due to lack of options and the struggle to get food on their plates. Nature is the epitome of fulfillment and fertility and so also food. Food which comes from nature is even controlled by the higher class to show the disparities on plate. The brahmanical ideologies of controlling habitats, natural resources, economy of the dalit community can be seen. Dalits are not allowed to choose food for themselves; they remain distant from nature in this manner where they have to take permission from the upper section of the society to get access to food. It's about food snobbery and imposing cultural hierarchy through food. What Dalits ate was always the food of poverty. They never felt that their food should be celebrated. What they ate was not the food prepared in abundance but that originated in the lack of ingredients and poverty in the kitchen.

Pawar mentions regarding the food disparity, "Our sisters-in-law, Nitha and Parvati, would also go begging along with other women in our community. They would carry baskets on their heads to collect the leftovers that might be given to them". "Some women would go to far-flung houses. They would carry with them separate containers and pots for collecting various dishes. But the Kulwadi women who gave them food would pour everything together in their baskets. Whatever they wanted to give – dal, vegetables, kheer-would all be poured on the rice, in a mixed mound. Women would bring back basketfuls of rice, in which many things were mixed. Not wanting the remaining rice to go rancid, they would put it into a basket, and hold it against the running water in the river. Shaking the basket against the flowing water, they would rinse it till only the clean rice remained in the basket. Sometimes they would wash the rice at home. They poured the insipid, cooked rice in an earthen pot and put it on the stove on low heat. Their entire house would survive for two days on those leftovers. In some houses the flesh of dead animals would be eaten. But that was forbidden in our house". While the dalits faced water discrimination, Pawar's father would always allowed everyone to use their well, the women would always come clean themselves, drink water and would take rest for sometime. Eating of carcass of animals remains the leftover choice of the dalit section as they were not allowed to eat fresh meat, traditionally it is being practiced, and they are not allowed to eat big fishes they have to survive on small fishes, dry smelly fishes. Pawar narrates how her childhood was spend in utter disgrace especially during her school days, while most of the students were off higher class they use to bring lavish tiffins which would always make her feel inferior and distinct her caste amongst her classmates, "The upper caste girls always used words like 'ladu', 'modak', 'Karanjya', 'Puranpoli'. They bought such novel items in their tiffin boxes as well at times when we went on excursions. They would also bring such food when they played with dolls. But I never asked myself stupid question, 'Why don't we make such dishes at home?' We were aware, without anybody telling us, that we were born in a particular caste and in poverty, and that we had to live accordingly.

Throughout the paper we discovered that how the interrelationship between caste, nature which results in unequal distribution of natural resources marked just a beginning of unraveling complexities of environmental injustices which has been projected by Pawar; whether it is the

connectedness of the Dalit community with nature and how they survive with nature or the kind of subjugation the society leveled on them through nature. The way dalits saw nature as the epitome of fulfillment amidst the hardship they faced in their daily life, whether it is the route they have to choose to do their daily works or food marginalization they went through. But nature acts the healing property to them, it remains very clear of how they treat nature. The relation between nature and caste remains visible through two way projection; one, the dalit treatment of nature and other, how upper caste used nature as a tool to victimize the dalits.

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